

Accessibility challenges at Joaquina Beach, Florianópolis, Brazil

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Abstract

The world lives in the age of the internet, real-time information, and a growing appreciation and concern for diversity across all areas of society. As a result of these transformations, discussions about the rights of people with disabilities and the challenges they face in navigating urban spaces and participating in various activities, including everyday tasks that should be guaranteed by law, as well as sports and leisure activities, have become more prominent. In this context, this study aimed to assess the accessibility conditions for people with disabilities at Joaquina Beach in Florianópolis, the capital of Santa Catarina, located in southern Brazil. This research is characterized as exploratory and descriptive, with an applied nature, and qualitative analysis. It was organized into two stages: a theoretical phase, including bibliographic and documentary research as primary investigative strategies, and a field phase, based on the application of a checklist to assess accessibility conditions on beaches. The checklist covered the following aspects: 1) Support points for specific assistance for people with disabilities; 2) Access routes; 3) Communication and signage; 4) Parking spaces for vehicles; 5) Toilets; and 6) Beaches. The results indicate that Joaquina Beach currently does not offer satisfactory accessibility conditions for people with disabilities or reduced mobility. Therefore, it is necessary to encourage and implement public policies that can provide better conditions for accessing the beach and waterfront facilities, ensuring greater autonomy and freedom for all individuals.

Key words: Accessibility, Brazil, Florianópolis, Joaquina Beach, Santa Catarina, waterfront

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Introduction

The number of people with disabilities reported in Brazil and globally has grown substantially in recent decades. This increase is attributed to the growing awareness of the main types of disabilities, and rising life expectancy, which heightens individuals' vulnerability to accidents and age-related physical impairments.

In Brazil, 18.6 million individuals, approximately 9% of the population, live with some form of disability, often facing barriers to exercising their constitutional right to freedom of movement (Brazilian Institute of Geography and Statistics [IBGE] 2023).

Another significant challenge in addressing this issue is the lack of updated official data, which hinders the development and implementation of effective public policies for inclusion and accessibility. Despite these challenges, a shift in societal perspectives has emerged, particularly in the field of tourism. According to Soares and Sánchez-Fernández (2018), the tourism industry historically marginalized people with disabilities due to inadequate infrastructure, a lack of specialized services, and insufficient training for personnel. These barriers limited access and participation for individuals with disabilities.

However, a relative paradigm shift can be observed among various tourism stakeholders, including public authorities, the private sector, academia, and society in general, as they gradually incorporate accessibility considerations into their actions. Increasingly, studies are focusing on integrating people with disabilities into tourism, promoting accessible environments, and advancing equity. For example, the Ministry of Tourism's (MTur) Accessible Tourism: Mapping the Profile of Tourists with Disabilities project aimed to "map the profile of these tourists and their travel habits, as well as analyze the influence of accessibility on the choice of destination and tourist attractions" (MTur 2023, n.p.).

In this study, the locus of analysis is Joaquina Beach, located on the eastern side of Florianópolis, the capital of Santa Catarina in southern Brazil. Joaquina Beach is not only one of the closest beaches to the city center (approximately 20 kilometers away) but also one of the most prominent in Florianópolis. It has hosted a variety of notable concerts and events, including international competitions, such as the World Surfing Championships of the first-division World Championship Tour (WCT) and the second-division World Surfing League (WSL), as well as performances by national and international artists, and numerous other initiatives.

Given its prominence, Joaquina Beach holds significant importance for tourism at local, state, and national levels. From this context, the research question arises: Is Joaquina Beach accessible for people with disabilities? This question also contributes to the important discussion of accessibility on Brazilian seafronts, particularly at high-profile locations such as this. While the study does not aim to generalize the findings, it seeks to foster critical reflections on accessibility in both Brazil and the global context.

To address this question, the research analyzed the accessibility conditions for people with disabilities at Joaquina Beach using a methodology inspired by prior studies conducted in the state of Paraíba. Specifically, the study applied the checklist presented in the publication 'Guia de Acessibilidade: Centro histórico e praias de João Pessoa/PB' (Accessibility Guide: Historic Center and beaches of João Pessoa, Paraíba). This methodology has been successfully implemented in another Brazilian state, and has been peer-reviewed and presented at Brazil's leading academic event in the field of tourism, where it received positive evaluations and constructive feedback for further improvement.

This research is further justified by the need to foster discussions that ensure all individuals, regardless of disability, have the right to access public and private spaces. Public policies must be developed and implemented to promote true inclusion, particularly for people with disabilities, in a wide range of spaces and activities. These policies must guarantee the rights of individuals with disabilities as outlined in the Brazilian Federal Constitution of 1988.

Although several bills related to the rights of people with disabilities are in progress, the Proposed Amendment to the Constitution n° 19 of 2014, commonly

referred to as the Accessibility PEC, is particularly noteworthy. This amendment seeks to revise Article 5 of the Federal Constitution to include the right to accessibility and mobility as fundamental individual and collective rights. This demonstrates the urgency of prioritizing accessibility in the national agenda.

In this context, this study emphasizes the analysis of accessibility at Joaquina Beach, advocating that tourism should serve as an inclusive practice that promotes equity. Ensuring accessibility in tourism allows all individuals to enjoy this fundamental right. In addition, this research aims to contribute to ongoing theoretical discussions on the intersection of tourism and accessibility. It offers a theoretical and critical framework that can inform scholars in tourism studies and related fields, such as public management, architecture, and urban planning, among others.

Literature review

People with disabilities, accessibility, and accessible tourism

Understanding the historical context of disability rights and accessibility is crucial to addressing the challenges faced by people with disabilities. According to Coutinho, Vanzella and Brambilla (2018), the issue began gaining international attention on December 9, 1975, during the United Nations (UN) General Assembly, when the first 'Declaration of the Rights of Persons with Disabilities' was approved. This declaration sought to amplify the voices of individuals with disabilities and establish their rights within society.

For much of history, as Nascimento et al. (2021) note, individuals with disabilities were neglected in society, and often perceived as incapable or limited. In addition to physical barriers to access, they faced prejudice and societal stigmas that hindered their full participation in social relationships. Over the years, the discussion on disability rights has gained increasing prominence, both globally and nationally.

Although the United Nations (UN) introduced the first 'Declaration of the Rights of Persons with Disabilities' in 1975, the debate on disabilities rights in Brazil gained prominence only with the creation of 'Federal Law No. 7.853, of 24 October 1989. This law broadly addressed support for people with disabilities and their social integration, as well as the creation of the National Coordination for the Integration of People with Disabilities (CORDE) (Brazil 1989, [s.p.]). It can therefore be said this law serves as the institutional framework that has shaped subsequent laws, decrees, and regulations across various sectors, including tourism.

It is important to emphasize that the requirement for accessible sites free from discrimination or barriers has been present in legislation since the Brazilian Federal Constitution of 1988. In its guidelines related to the right of Brazilian citizens to move freely, Article 5, item XV, states: 'Locomotion within the national territory is free in times of peace, and anyone may, in accordance with the law, enter, remain, or leave it with their goods' (Brazil 1988). This underscores that providing accessibility to ensure.

All citizens can move freely is not a favor or an extra benefit, but rather a right guaranteed by law.

Overall, it can be asserted that the Brazilian Federal Government has undertaken various initiatives to better understand and address accessibility

challenges in the country. Data collected through the 2010 Demographic Census, the National Health Survey (PNS) 2013 and 2019, and the Continuous National Household Sample Survey (Pnad) of 2022, among others, shed light on the primary difficulties faced by people with disabilities:

The most reported difficulty was walking or climbing steps (3.4 %), followed by seeing, even with corrective lenses (3.1 %); learning, remembering things, or concentrating (2.6 %); lifting a two-liter bottle of water from waist to eye level (2.3%); picking up small objects or opening and closing containers (1.4%); hearing, even with hearing aids (1.2%); performing personal care tasks (1.2%); and communicating effectively (1.1%). Additionally, 5.5% of individuals reported a disability in only one function, while 3.4 % experienced difficulties in two or more functions (IBGE 2023).

According to the IBGE (2010), for some years and even today, terms such as people with special needs and people with disabilities have been used to refer to individuals with disabilities. However, these terms are now considered inappropriate. As Carvalho-Freitas and Marques (2006) argue, the term people with special needs is overly broad, encompassing diverse groups requiring special treatment, such as pregnant women, obese individuals, and the elderly, rather than specifically addressing individuals with disabilities. On the other hand, Sasaki (2002) emphasizes that the term people with disabilities is outdated because it suggests the individual is defined by the disability, which is conceptually flawed.

Following this contextualization, and within the scope of this study, it is worth specifying the issue of accessibility for people with disabilities in the context of tourism, namely, what laws exist or what guarantees are in place for travelers with specific needs to enable their Mobility across territories. Within this theme, according to Hoyo and Valient (2010), the World Tourism Organization (UNWTO) began discussing the issue of accessibility in tourism in 1980, during the Manila Declaration (Philippines). This event was a significant milestone as it recognized and promoted tourism as a fundamental and necessary right for all.

In Brazil, the discussion of accessibility in tourism gained prominence in the constitutional framework, but it was not until 1999 that the issue was formally addressed as a concrete objective with the enactment of Decree No. 3,298, dated December 20, 1999:

[...] to ensure that people with disabilities can fully exercise their fundamental rights, including rights to education, health, work, sports, tourism, leisure, social security, social assistance, transportation, public buildings, housing, culture, child and maternity support, among others deriving from the Constitution and laws, to provide for their personal, social, and economic well-being (Brazil 1999, [s.p.]).

This decree was designed to regulate Federal Law No. 7,853 of October 24, 1989, presenting details for the operation of tourism and leisure while emphasizing the right of people with disabilities to participate fully in these activities. It aimed to encourage municipal and state agencies to develop public policies that promote the integration of this public.

A notable example is Law 10.098/2000, known in Brazil as the 'Accessibility Law'. This law focuses on eliminating physical and social barriers that hinder access for individuals with disabilities (Brasil 2000). Complementing this, Decree 5.296/2004 reinforces the commitment to creating accessible environments and guarantees conditions for the independent or assisted use of communication and information systems (Brasil 2004).

In response to these legislative efforts, the Ministry of Tourism (MTur) launched two key publications, the 2006 booklet called 'Tourism and Accessibility: Guidelines Manual', and the 2009 booklet 'Accessible Tourism: Introduction to an Inclusive Journey'. Both publications provided practical guidance on implementing accessibility features and addressed both theoretical and practical aspects of accessible tourism (Neis et al. 2018).

To clarify the scope of accessibility, the MTur (2006, p. 14) defines a person with a disability as someone who experiences limitations or incapacity in performing certain activities due to physical, hearing, visual, mental, or multiple disabilities (a combination of two or more impairments). Accordingly, tourism spaces must be designed to ensure that everyone, regardless of their abilities, can fully access and enjoy the country's offerings. For the Ministry of Tourism, accessibility means 'enabling people with disabilities or reduced mobility to enjoy social environments, equipment, and furniture, as well as buildings, transport systems and means of communication and information safely and autonomously'.

These two concepts are extremely important to form the foundation for the manuals and guidelines developed to promote accessible tourism. By adhering to these principles, stakeholders can create inclusive environments that uphold the rights of all individuals and offer opportunities to explore the rich diversity of tourism experiences.

Building on these efforts, the Ministry of Tourism partnered with the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) to launch the document 'Accessible Tourism: Mapping the profile of tourists with disabilities', with the following objectives and results:

The initiative aims to map the profile and travel habits of tourists with disabilities while analyzing the impact of accessibility on their choice of destinations and attractions. Data collection was conducted through a questionnaire targeting two groups: tourists with disabilities (physical, sensory, or mental/intellectual) and tourists with reduced mobility, such as the elderly, obese individuals, pregnant women, or those experiencing temporary mobility challenges that do not qualify as physical disabilities. The majority of respondents identified as having physical disabilities (34.91%), followed by individuals with intellectual or mental disabilities or autistic spectrum disorder (12.11%) (MTur 2023, n.p.).

Although it is possible to see that Brazilian governments have made efforts to promote accessible tourism through legislation and its inclusion in Tourism Plans, the responsibility for ensuring the effectiveness of these measures lies with the tourism management of each Federative Entity and Municipality. This involves creating spaces, roads, enterprises, and signage that comply with legal requirements and uphold the rights of all individuals, ensuring an inclusive and effective practice of tourism activities.

Joaquina Beach - Florianópolis, Santa Catarina, Brazil

Joaquina Beach, commonly known as 'Joaca', is situated in Florianópolis, on the island of Santa Catarina, in southern Brazil, approximately 20 km from the city's urban center. It is one of the beaches within the Joaquina Beach arch (Fig. 1), and is characterized by a large influx of tourists, particularly those interested in Adventure Tourism. The beach is a popular destination for extreme sports such as sandboarding and surfing, as its wave conditions attract surfers from across the region (Viaje Mais 2022).

Figure 1. Joaquina Beach, Florianópolis, Santa Catarina, Brazil. Photo from the authors' personal collection, 2023.

From this perspective, the attraction in question has the potential to captivate visitors, drawing them from their usual locales to attend events such as surfing championships or cultural performances. Joaquina Beach also offers basic infrastructure to accommodate visitors, including public restrooms, shops, restaurants, bars, lodging establishments, nightclubs, and traditional surf schools, which introduce beginners to the sport.

Online reviews highlight the beach's widespread appeal. For instance, it has received over 28,000 reviews on Google Maps and more than 7,000 on the travel site TripAdvisor from visitors hailing from various regions of Brazil and around the world (Google Inc 2023; TripAdvisor 2023). These reviews emphasize its popularity among traveling families, surfers, and sandboarding enthusiasts with a sport practiced on the dunes of Joaca as a variation of surfing.

The following map (Fig. 2) illustrates the location of Joaquina Beach and its surrounding infrastructure. Key elements such as Édio's Sandboard, lodging facilities, and the Pedra Careca Restaurant enhance the tourist experience. The availability of these services is essential to maintaining Joaquina Beach as a high-quality tourist destination, ensuring its continued popularity among visitors.

The profile of tourists visiting the town is diverse. According to data from the Florianópolis Tourism Bureau (Setur 2018), most visitors originate from São Paulo, are between 30 and 39 years old, and stay an average of 8 days at the

Figure 2. Generated using Google Maps, 2023. Territorial extension of Joaquina Beach.

destination. Tourist motivations vary, with the most popular segments being adventure, nature and ecotourism (34.6%), gastronomy (25.2%), and culture (29.4%). Despite this variety, the sun and beach segment remains the primary attraction, drawing 71.2% of visitors (Setur 2018).

Methodology

The research is characterized as descriptive and exploratory, applied in nature, with qualitative analysis. It was organized in two stages: a theoretical phase and a field-based phase. The main research strategies included bibliographical research on topics such as individuals with disabilities, accessibility, and sun-and-beach tourism, using databases such as Google Scholar, Scopus, and Web of Science.

Documentary research was conducted on documents from the Brazilian Association of Technical Standards (ABNT), specifically NBR 9050/2015, as well as official data from the Brazilian Institute of Geography and Statistics (IBGE) on individuals with disabilities and the Ministry of Tourism's technical document 'Turismo Acessível: Mapeamento do perfil do turista com deficiência' (Accessible Tourism: Mapping the profile of tourists with disabilities).

Field data collection took place in May 2023, during the low tourist season in the city, and consisted of two stages. The first stage involved a macro-level analysis of the area, focusing on the route connecting Lagoa da Conceição to Joaquina Beach (the main access route), comprising approximately three kilometers of road and sidewalks.

On this route, general accessibility features were observed, including sidewalk conditions, tourist signage, and the overall level of difficulty for pedestrians and wheelchair users navigating the route, among other aspects, as shown in (Fig. 3).

The second stage focused on the arrival and beachfront area, which also has approximately three kilometers and includes various attractions such as restaurants, parking areas, and a small central hub with shops, and handicrafts, among other amenities.

Figure 3. Access to Joaquina Beach. Generated using Google Maps, 2023.

During the second visit, the beach accessibility conditions checklist proposed by Melo, Brambilla, and Vanzella (2020) was applied. To better suit the target audience of the study, the model was adapted to include the following aspects: 1) Support points for specific assistance for individuals with disabilities; 2) Access; 3) Communication and signage; 4) Parking spaces; 5) Restrooms; and 6) Beaches. The tool consists of 68 items related to these aspects. The checklist was developed based on ABNT's NBR 9050/2015 and the guidance booklet on sun-and-beach tourism produced by MTur (2010).

Finally, the data were synthesized and analyzed, allowing the research to fulfill its purpose of contributing to discussions on accessibility in beach and shoreline management. Based on the field data, complemented by the theoretical framework, the results were discussed and the conclusions of the research were drawn.

Discussion and results

As previously mentioned, in order to assess the accessibility conditions for individuals with disabilities at Joaquina Beach, Florianópolis, capital of the state of Santa Catarina, Brazil, the checklist was applied at key points along the access road and beachfront, at two different times.

Along the approximately 3 kilometers of road connecting Lagoa da Conceição to Joaquina Beach (the main access route), the focus was on verifying aspects related to accessibility, such as the presence of sidewalks with connecting ramps, tourist signage, and other relevant factors, as illustrated below.

Several issues were identified in terms of general accessibility, including the existence of regular sidewalks with tactile paving, adequate width, good maintenance, accessible ramps, some steep gradients, few obstacles along the route, raised lanes, and well-marked pedestrian crossings. However, issues with tourist signage were also noted. "Figure 3: Lagoa da Conceição (Conceição Lagoon)" indicates the starting point for the first stage of field data collection, which aimed to analyze access to the beach. Figs 4–8 show that the road is in good condition, with a pedestrian crossing, sidewalk, and bike lane, along with tourist signs, a strong connection to nature, and unique scenic beauty. However, not all sections of the route are in the same condition, and some stretches feature steeper gradients.

Figure 4. Lagoa da Conceição. Photo from the authors' personal collection, 2023.

Figure 5. Access road with pedestrian crossing. Photo from the authors' personal collection, 2023.

Figure 6. Tourist signage. Photo from the authors' personal collection, 2023.

Figure 7. Proper sidewalk and bike lane. Photo from the authors' personal collection, 2023.

Figure 8. Uneven surfaces along the route. Photo from the authors' personal collection, 2023.

Figure 9. Bike lane, scenic beauty, and nature.. Photo from the authors' personal collection, 2023.

Figure 10. Bus parking. Photo from the authors' personal collection, 2023.

Figure 11. Joaquina street fair. Photo from the authors' personal collection, 2023.

As seen in Fig. 11: Main access to the beach, it is evident that there was no concern about the mobility needs of wheelchair users, individuals with reduced mobility, or those who are visually impaired concerning the primary access to the beach and the sea bathing area. The photo shows a staircase with numerous steps, no handrail, and no access ramp. Beyond the stairs, the sand area offers no adaptations to meet the needs of these individuals, making access impossible.

According to a survey by the Ministry of Tourism mapping the profile of tourists with disabilities, physical disability (34.91%) was the most prevalent (MTur 2023). This data shows the importance of addressing accessibility issues, as structural barriers hinder autonomy and freedom for these individuals, particularly when enjoying public spaces.

The second part of the data analysis focused on the application and interpretation of the checklist along the seafront, covering aspects such as: 1) support point for specific services; 2) access; 3) communication and signage; 4) parking spaces; restrooms; and 6) the beach.

In general, no 'support points for specific assistance' were identified during the survey, nor were accessible public restrooms found. Although a ramp is located

at the main beach access point, other paths are in poor condition, with obstacles such as stairs, steep gradients, barriers, lack of signage, and inadequate maintenance, among other impediments.

Overall, the waterfront area also lacks adequate services, infrastructure, communication, and signage. However, it does provide car parking spaces for individuals with disabilities, some access ramps, accessible public showers, unique scenic beauty, as well as shops, food and beverage services, and lodging facilities, among other features, as shown in Fig. 12 and Fig. 22.

Figure 12. Lack of ramp to the beach. Photo from the authors' personal collection, 2023.

Figure 13. Partial access ramps. Photo from the authors' personal collection, 2023.

Figure 14. Car parking. Photo from the authors' personal collection, 2023.

Figure 15. Ramps between sidewalks. Photo from the authors' personal collection, 2023.

Figure 16. Access to the beach's coastline. Photo from the authors' personal collection, 2023.

Figure 17. Beach sand strip. Photo from the authors' personal collection, 2023.

Figure 18. Showers and accessible access. Photo from the authors' personal collection, 2023.

Figure 19. Car parking. Photo from the authors' personal collection, 2023.

Figure 20. Accessible public shower. Photo from the authors' personal collection, 2023.

Figure 21. Dunes of Joaquina Beach. Photo from the authors' personal collection, 2023.

Figure 22. Beach access stairway. Photo from the authors' personal collection, 2023.

This research delves deeper into the items on the checklist, offering brief observations on each of the six quadrants analyzed: 1. Support point for specific services; 2. Access to Joaquina Beach; 3. Communication and signage; 4. Parking spaces and signage; 5. Accessible restrooms; and 6. Beaches.

- 1. Support point for specific assistance:** This section examines aspects related to physical infrastructure intended to assist people with disabilities. This includes the existence of a specific tourist assistance center (TAC), staff trained in accessibility matters, professional qualification initiatives aimed at this public, among other factors. Although a TAC exists, no substantial infrastructure was identified, and no efforts were made in this area during the low season.
- 2. Access to Joaquina Beach:** This section analyzes infrastructure-related aspects such as pavement conditions, access ramps, obstacles, pedestrian crossings, stairs, and tactile paving. Overall, the access surfaces were found to be mostly in good condition, with wide pavements and tactile flooring, but some obstacles were identified. A significant issue highlighted was the transition zone between the urbanized area and the beach, as only one access ramp was in good condition, and there were no adapted pathways leading to the sea.
- 3. Communication and Signage:** Effective communication and signage are crucial for accessibility. This section evaluates the availability of indicators, whether they are permanent or temporary, the presence of emergency signage, tactile maps, and auditory cues, among other variables. It was noted that there is limited information available, mostly related to traffic and tourist signs, which is another item that requires urgent intervention from public authorities.

The Ministry of Tourism, through the National Tourism Plan (2018–2022), pointed out the lack of accessible information in tourist services, noting that ‘limited accessibility information, discrimination, and negative experiences discourage these potential consumers’ (MTur 2018, p.45–46).

This reality was confirmed by the survey on the profile of tourists with disabilities, in which respondents emphasized the importance of having adequate and accurate information on accessibility for each type of disability. Such information enables travelers to avoid inconvenience when deciding where to go or how to best experience the locations (MTur 2023). It is precisely in this area that public planners need to focus greater attention, working to promote the insertion of accessibility signage, not only on urban signs but also on tourist signs for all attractions in a destination.

It is also important to note that visual impairment is the disability that most affects Brazilians (IBGE 2010), yet they are the tourists who most frequently travel alone (MTur 2023). Therefore, investing in the communication and signposting process for this public is crucial in providing travelers with greater autonomy in various locales.

- 4. Parking spaces:** Reserved and specially designated parking spaces are crucial for managing waterfront areas with the goal of promoting accessibility. Key factors include the allocation of an adequate number of

designated spots and the presence of accessible vertical and horizontal signage, among other considerations. Regarding these items, the field research observed a good response to the diverse needs.

5. Restrooms: The availability of public restrooms at visitor sites is another key factor to consider. Details such as the accessibility of the route to these facilities, the adequate number of units (5%), the presence of support bars, and accessible urinals, among other aspects, are important. However, the public restrooms were not open during both data collection periods, and only the restrooms in local restaurants and shops were observed. Overall, the accessibility of this item was not adequately addressed.

6. Beaches: Since the research aims to analyze the accessibility of Joaquina Beach, the primary goal for people with disabilities visiting the location is to experience swimming in the sea, strolling around the area, participating in water-based recreational activities with peers, and, if possible, with trained personnel available for support when needed. Unfortunately, this was not the reality for people attempting to swim at the studied site, as several structures that should facilitate this activity were missing.

Several Brazilian states have projects that enable people with disabilities to better enjoy beach activities, such as Projeto Praia para Todos (RJ), Praia Sem Barreiras (PE), Praia Acessível (SP), and Projeto AC Social (PB). These initiatives could serve as models for implementation at the studied site, enhancing entertainment opportunities and providing moments of socialization for the disabled community who visits or would like to visit Joaquina Beach.

These projects are philanthropic in nature and supported by municipal governments, state authorities, and third-sector organizations, all of which collaborate to improve conditions and safeguard the rights of disabled residents and tourists. They are also capable of raising funds to purchase equipment, such as amphibious chairs and accessible mats, which enhance mobility. Additionally, they establish partnerships with volunteers from various fields to assist with accessible sports and healthcare.

The following presents a summary of the findings from the field research (Table 1), where a list of the positive and negative aspects observed during the on-site study can be seen.

Table 1. Summary of field research findings.

Positive aspects	Negative aspects
Parking for seniors and people with disabilities (PWD).	It does not have a support point or tourist information available during the low season.
It has wide sidewalks and a bike lane.	It does not have beach access for wheelchair users.
Reference modules.	Absence of amphibious chairs.
Tactile floor.	Lack of adapted toilets.
Painted pedestrian crosswalk.	Absence of free physical activities.
Signage for parking and integration into an accessible Route.	It does not have adapted circulation structures in the beach area (sand strip).
Beach access ramp.	Lack of a tactile horizontal map.
Existence of public restrooms.	Absence of trained attendants for assistance and support, if necessary.

Source: Elaborated by the authors, 2023.

The summary of the results indicates the negative aspects outweigh the positive ones. Therefore, it can be concluded that although Joaquina Beach has some elements that support accessibility, the site still lacks satisfactory conditions to accommodate people with disabilities or reduced mobility.

As a result, both public and private sector managers need to pay closer attention to this issue, promoting the creation of public policies that support and foster universal access across various structures at destinations. This will enable more people with disabilities to travel, which, in turn, will allow destinations to welcome an increasing number of travelers, improving the overall quality of tourism.

Conclusion

The research provided several insights into the accessibility and management of seafronts at Joaquina Beach in Florianópolis, Santa Catarina, Brazil, conducted during a period considered to be the low season. These reflections were based on analyses previously carried out by researchers in Paraíba, who developed a checklist organized into 6 topics for analysis. The empirical validation of this checklist in a different context from the one in which it was originally created represents the study's primary contribution.

Field research data were collected in two stages. Based on this analysis tool, a series of factors related to the accessibility of the waterfront (3 km) and access routes (3 km) were identified, including the existence of a relatively even access surface, sidewalks with widths well exceeding the minimum required, many of which had tactile flooring and were in good condition. The presence of restaurants, a market, and local shops were also positive factors.

Another relevant infrastructure element is the presence of an access ramp to the beach sand; however, it lacks any mechanisms (such as handrails) to ensure that people with disabilities or reduced mobility can safely reach their desired destination, which, in this case, is swimming in the sea. Obstacles were also identified, including the transition area between the urbanized section and the sea, inadequate signage, communication failures, and a lack of public toilets, among other bottlenecks requiring intervention and adaptation.

Overall, the results suggest that Joaquina Beach does not meet satisfactory accessibility conditions for people with disabilities or reduced mobility. Therefore, it is essential to promote public policies that improve accessibility to the beach and its facilities, thereby ensuring greater autonomy and freedom for all individuals, without exception.

The primary limitation of this study is that it was conducted at only one beach in Florianópolis, with data collection limited to the low season. Additional limitations include time constraints and limited resources. However, this study could be expanded by repeating the research during the high season, capturing tourists' perceptions of beach accessibility, and investigating other beaches in Florianópolis, other cities, states, and countries, as well as exploring numerous other possibilities.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statement

No ethical statement was reported.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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